

Advancing equity of health service accessibility through spatial analysis: Applying the 3-step floating catchment area method for examining physiotherapy in Aotearoa New Zealand

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Unequal access to health care contributes to disparities in health outcomes. Physiotherapy services can play a major role in conditions that excessively burden Aotearoa New Zealand (NZ) Māori, Pacific, high socioeconomic deprivation and rural populations. However, the distribution of the NZ physiotherapy workforce relative to these populations is not known. This study demonstrates a novel application of the distance-based 3-step floating catchment area (3SFCA) method to examine the distribution of NZ physiotherapy workforce spatial accessibility at a high acuity level stratified by demographic indicators of health need (Māori or Pacific ethnicity, socioeconomic deprivation, rurality).

Geocoded physiotherapy workforce data for 5,582 physiotherapists (92% of the 6,038 registered physiotherapists at March 2022) were integrated with 2018 NZ Census data to generate 'accessibility scores' (weighted practitioner: population ratio) for each Statistical Area 2 using the 3SFCA method. Demographic characteristics of rurality, Māori ethnicity, Pacific ethnicity, and socioeconomic deprivation were categorised based on pre-defined rationale, cross tabulated with accessibility scores, and thematically mapped using ArcGIS software. Trends in relationships were explored statistically using correlation techniques.

The study identified specific geographic locations of inequity where health need is high, yet accessibility of physiotherapy is low (<0.94 to 9.06 per 10,000). In particular were areas in the mid-central North Island, west and northern Northland, and the East Coast. In comparison, areas of highest accessibility included the South Island lakes district and central Canterbury (up to 26/10,000). The mean accessibility score was 11.88 per 10,000. At a national level, low physiotherapy accessibility was statistically associated with high proportion population Māori ethnicity and more rural location. The methods developed in this study can be implemented regionally to help establish profiles of health services that meet local population needs.